

Maio 2023

Herpetologia Brasileira

volume 12 número 1
ISSN: 2316-4670

Herpetologia Brasileira

Uma publicação da Sociedade
Brasileira de Herpetologia

Sociedade Brasileira de Herpetologia
www.sbherpetologia.org.br

Presidente: Denise de C. Rossa-Feres

1º Secretária: Paula Hanna Valdujo

2º Secretária: Bianca Von Muller Berneck

1º Tesoureira: Karina Rodrigues da Silva Banci

2º Tesoureira: Ariadne Fares Sabbag

Conselho: Christine Strussmann, Délio Baêta, Helio Ricardo da Silva, José Perez Pombal Junior, Luciana B. Nascimento, Márcio R. C. Martins, Mariana Lyra, Otávio A. V. Marques, Taran Grant e Thais Helena Condez

Membros Honorários: Augusto S. Abe, Carlos Alberto Gonçalves da Cruz, Ivan Sazima, Luis Dino Vizotto, Miguel Trefaut Urbano Rodrigues, Teresa Cristina Sauer de Avila-Pires, Ulisses Caramaschi.

Diagramação: Isadora Puntel de Almeida

Bothrops bilineatus
Aripuanã, MT
@ Henrique C. Costa

ISSN: 2316-4670
volume 12 número 1
Maio de 2023

SBH
SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE
HERPETOLOGIA

Giants above us: two field observations of anacondas hunting on trees

Anderson Lozorio C. F.^{1*}, Angelica B. Leite², Julio C. F. Proença-Gomes³, Thiago Silva-Soares⁴

1 Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazônia, Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciências de Florestas Tropicais, 69060-001 Manaus, AM, Brazil.

2 Biology undergrad student at Universidade Estácio de Sá, 25550-100 Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil.

3 Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ecologia e Evolução, 20950-000 Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil.

4 Instituto Biodiversidade Neotropical, Herpeto Capixaba project, Rua Sanhaço 562, Nova Guarapari, 29206-400 Guarapari, ES, Brazil.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: andersonlozorio@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7828889](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828889)

Predation is a major factor affecting population dynamics in ecosystems and their microhabitats, since a small number of predators may be sufficient to regulate an entire prey population (Odum, 1986; Ricklefs, 2003). Competition for food and adaptations to overcome prey defenses have given rise to refined morpho-physiological and behavioral mechanisms to find, capture and eat other animals (Owen, 1980). Each environment shows different levels of complexity that exerts a pressure on the phenotypes of organisms, and the interaction between behavior and morphol-

ogy will ultimately influence the way in which each organism uses the resources available in the environment (Miles & Ricklefs, 1984). Understanding the intrinsic relationship between snake predatory behavior and their different habits may allow a better analysis of their occurrence in their microhabitats, besides corroborating the importance of preserving natural habitats (Ford, 1995; Cundall & Greene, 2000).

The Neotropical boid genus *Eunectes* (translates as “good swimmer”) includes four extant species: the Bolivian Anaconda, *Eunectes beniensis* Dirksen,

2002, the Dark-spotted Anaconda, *E. deschauenseei* Dunn & Conant, 1936, the Green Anaconda, *E. murinus* (Linnaeus, 1758), and the Yellow Anaconda, *E. notaeus* Cope, 1862 (Uetz et al., 2022). Anacondas are distributed in all lowlands of tropical South America east of the Andes (Thorbjarnarson, 1995; Rivas et al., 2007; Tarkhnishvili et al., 2022), and are usually closely associated with lakes and rivers, being the most specialized giant snakes in their preferred habitat (Murphy & Henderson, 1997). They are semi-aquatic and many morphological characters are adaptations for this lifestyle: narrower ventral scales, relatively small eyes and nostrils on top of head, with some species having a dark olive/greenish coloration with black spots with lighter centers that blend perfectly with the aquatic vegetation (Rivas, 1999). Anacondas are specialized for aquatic hunting, where they sit and wait for prey to approach with only eyes and nostrils above the water surface and they may go for long periods without a meal (Thorbjarnarson, 1995; Pizzatto et al., 2009).

The green anaconda *E. murinus* is one of the longest snake species worldwide, and is clearly the heaviest (Rivas, 1999). There are reports of 10–12 meter anacondas weighing up to 250 kg (Rivas, 1999), although the actual maximum size of an anaconda is the subject of much debate (Rivas, 1999; Rivas & Burghardt, 2001). These vi-

viparous snakes show marked sexual size dimorphism, with females attaining much larger sizes than males (Duellman, 2005). They are opportunistic apex predators, feeding on any prey that they can kill and swallow, usually ranging from 14% to 50% of its own mass (O’Shea, 2007). Despite the prominence of *Eunectes* species in popular culture, there are few syntheses on their diet. Recently, Thomas & Allain (2021) presented an extensive study on prey items previously published in scientific literature, providing the first summary of diet across all four *Eunectes* species. The results indicate that *E. murinus* are trophically opportunistic and have a broad diet, taking a large variety of prey items that appears to vary ontogenetically, with juveniles feeding on birds more often than adults (Thomas & Allain, 2021). The prey includes all aquatic and terrestrial vertebrate groups, including a large diversity of fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals (Miranda et al. 2016; Thomas & Allain, 2021). Anacondas swallow their prey whole and are considered gape-limited predators, with the size of prey being determined by the diameter of the snake’s head (King, 2002).

Herein we report the first record of *Eunectes murinus* preying on a Brown-throated three-toed sloth, *Bradypus variegatus* Schinz, 1825 (Fig. 1). On 24 March 2022, at 09:02, during a tour on the banks of the Juruá River

(-4.8343°, -66.7768°; WGS84; 80 m above sea level), in the municipality of Carauari, state of Amazonas, Northern Brazil, a group of tourists observed an adult *E. murinus* of about 3500 mm total length. It was on branches of a Fabaceae tree at about 4 m above the water level. The group guide, Ismael Nascimento, recorded a video that shows the snake in the process of swallowing the sloth, with about one third of the sloth already consumed. The predation event occurred in a dense ombrophilous alluvial forest, also known as “Igapó”, the vegetation that occurs along black and clear water rivers that are periodically flooded (Junk et al., 2011).

The sloth was identified as *B. variegatus* because of its brown colored throat and sides of the face, continuing on chest and shoulders; dark brown forehead and a suborbital stripe outlining the paler color of the ocular area (Wetzel, 1985). The sloth is a common inhabitant of primary and secondary evergreen and semi-deciduous forests. They occur from southern Honduras to northern Argentina, usually dwelling in high tree strata in various ecosystems, such as dry and rain forests (Eisenberg & Redford, 1989; Magnusson, 1997). The snake was identified as *E. murinus* by its characteristic dark olive-green dorsum, gradually changing to yellow ventrally, with round brown dorsal blotches with diffused black edges along the mid to posterior length of its

body (Rivas, 1999). The event occurred within the known geographic range of *E. murinus* (Amorós & Manrique, 2008) and *B. variegatus* (Ruiz-García et al., 2020).

We also present a record of predation of an adult Green Iguana, *Iguana iguana* (Linnaeus, 1758) by *E. murinus*, at the top of a tree (Fig. 2). The Green Iguana is a tropical lizard, a folivore species when adult, with diurnal and preferably arboreal habits (Rand & Rand, 1976; Dugan, 1982). Two young individuals with estimated snout-vent length between 180 and 239 mm were formerly reported as prey of *E. murinus* (Rivas, 1999; Thomas & Allain, 2021). There is no information whether those individuals were captured in trees or on the ground. On 27 March 2017, at 15:30, during a tourist incursion on Tucunaré Lake (-3.6763°, -59.868°; WGS 84; 20 m a.s.l.), in the municipality of Careiro, Amazonas, Brazil, Ismael Nascimento spotted a ca. 3 m long anaconda on tree branches at about three meters above the water level in a “várzea” – floodplain ecosystems influenced by periodic floods of sediment-loaded, nutrient-rich white-water rivers (Prance, 1979). Ismael recorded the moment in a video that shows the anaconda constricting and swallowing the adult iguana, with only the hind legs and tail visible. In the final seconds of the video, the snake falls into the water while consuming the iguana.

To our knowledge, records presented here are the second and third records of *Eunectes murinus* consuming prey in trees (Freitas, 2009). Both predation events occurred during flood seasons (March 2017 and 2022), when the water level of most rivers in the Amazon basin is high and increasing (Da Silva et al., 2012). Therefore, it is reasonable to hypothesize that some *E. murinus* individuals/populations in flooded forests of Amazonia are forced to hunt in trees when the flood pulse reaches their foraging areas. Videos of the predation of the sloth and the iguana are available online at <https://www.herpetocapixaba.com.br/herpetovideos>

Both records came from field observation of professional guides that spend most of their time in the Amazon Forest. It is worthy of note how important it is to promote citizen science and work together with local people.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the professional guides Kennedy William and Ismael Nascimento for providing videos and information reported herein. This work is part of the projects: ‘Biotrips: science in biological tourism in the Amazon’ and ‘Herpeto Capixaba: for the knowledge and conservation of amphibians and reptiles of Brazil’. TSS thanks support from Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo

(EDITAL FAPES Nº 03/2021 - UNIVERSAL #437/2021).

REFERENCES

Amorós C.L.B., Manrique R. 2008. Observations on the Natural History of the Green Anaconda (*Eunectes murinus* Linnaeus, 1758) in the Venezuelan Llanos: An Ecotourism Perspective. *Iguana* 15:92–101.

Cundall D., Greene H.W. 2000. Feeding in snakes. Pp. 293–333, in Schwenk K. (Ed.), *Feeding: form, function and evolution in tetrapod vertebrates*. Academic Press, San Diego. doi:[10.1016/B978-012632590-4/50010-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012632590-4/50010-1).

Da Silva J.S., Seyler F., Calmant S., Rotunno-Filho O.C., Roux E., Araújo A.A.M., Guyot J.L. 2012. Water level dynamics of Amazon wetlands at the watershed scale by satellite altimetry. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 33:3323–3353. doi:[10.1080/01431161.2010.531914](https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2010.531914).

Duellman W.E. 2005. *Cusco Amazonico: The Lives of Amphibians and Reptiles in an Amazonian Rainforest*. Comstock Books in Herpetology, Ithaca.

Dugan B. 1982. The mating behavior of the green iguana, *Iguana iguana*. Pp. 320–339, in Burghardt G., Rand A.S. (Eds.). *Iguanas of the world: their behavior, ecology, and conservation*. Noyes Publication, New Jersey.

- Eisenberg J.F., Redford K.H. 1989. Mammals of the Neotropics, Volume 3: Ecuador, Bolivia, Brazil (Vol. 3). University of Chicago Press, Chicago. doi:10.4067/S0716-078X2005000200017
- Ford N.B. 1995. Experimental design in studies of snake behavior. *Herpetological Monographs* 9:130–139. doi:10.2307/1467001.
- Freitas D. 2009. *Eunectes murinus* (Green Anaconda). Diet. *Herpetological Review* 40:98.
- Junk W.J., Piedade M.T.F., Schöngart J., Cohn-Haft M., Adeney J.M., Wittmann F. 2011. A classification of major naturally-occurring Amazonian lowland wetlands. *Wetlands* 31:623–640. doi:10.1007/s13157-011-0190-7.
- King R.B. 2002. Predicted and observed maximum prey size-snake size allometry. *Functional Ecology* 19(6):766–772. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2435.2002.00678.x.
- Magnusson W.E. 1997. Neotropical rainforest mammals: a field guide. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Miles D.B., Ricklefs R.E. 1984. The correlation between ecology and morphology in deciduous forest passerine birds. *Ecology* 65:1629–1640. doi:10.2307/1939141.
- Miranda E.B., Ribeiro Jr. R.P., Strüssmann C. 2016. The ecology of human anaconda conflict: A study using internet videos. *Tropical Conservation Science* 9:43–77. doi:10.1177/194008291600900105.
- Murphy J.C., Henderson R.W. 1997. Tales of giant snakes: a historical natural history of anacondas and pythons. Krieger Publishing Company, Florida.
- O’Shea M. 2007. Boas and Pythons of the World. New Holland, London.
- Odum E.P. 1986. Ecologia. Editora Guanabara Koogan, Rio de Janeiro.
- Owen D.F. 1980. Camouflage and Mimicry. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Pizzatto L., Marques O.A.V., Facure K. 2009. Food habits of Brazilian boid snakes: overview and new data, with special reference to *Corallus hortulanus*. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 30:533–544. doi:10.1163/156853809789647121.
- Prance G.T., 1979. Notes on the vegetation of Amazonia III. The terminology of Amazonian forest types subject to inundation. *Brittonia* 3:26–38. doi:10.2307/2806669
- Rand W.M., Rand A.S. 1976. Agonistic behavior in nesting iguanas: a stochastic analysis of dispute settlement dominated by the minimi-

zation of energy cost. *Zeitschrift für Tierpsychologie* 40:279–299. doi:[10.1111/j.1439-0310.1976.tb00938](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0310.1976.tb00938).

Ricklefs R.E. 2003. A economia da natureza. Editora Guanabara Koogan, Rio de Janeiro.

Rivas J.A. 1999. The life history of the Green Anaconda (*Eunectes murinus*), with emphasis on its reproductive biology. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Tennessee, USA.

Rivas J.A., Burghardt, G.M. 2001. Understanding sexual size dimorphism in snakes: wearing the snake's shoes. *Animal Behaviour* 62:F1–F6. doi:[10.1006/anbe.2001.1755](https://doi.org/10.1006/anbe.2001.1755).

Rivas J.A., Munoz M.C., Thorbjarnarson J.B., Burghardt G.M., Holmstrom W., Calle P. 2007. Natural history of the Green Anacondas in the Venezuelan llanos. Pp. 128–138., in Henderson R.W., Powell R. (Eds.), *Biology of Boas, Pythons, and Related Taxa*. Eagle Mountain Publishing, Eagle Mountain.

Ruiz-García M., Chacón D., Plese T., Shostell J. M. 2020. Molecular phylogenetics of *Bradypus* (three-toed sloth, Pilosa: Bradypodidae, Mammalia) and phylogeography of *Bradypus variegatus* (brown-throated three-toed sloth) with mitochondrial gene sequences. *Journal of Mammalian Evolution* 27:461–482. doi:[10.1007/s10914-019-09465-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10914-019-09465-w).

Tarkhnishvili D., Hille A., Waller T., Todua M., Murtskhvaladze M., Böhme W. 2022. Morphological trends and genetic divergence in anacondas, genus *Eunectes* Wagler, 1830 (Serpentes: Boidae). *Amphibia-Reptilia* 43:379–393. doi:[10.1163/15685381-bja10114](https://doi.org/10.1163/15685381-bja10114).

Thomas O., Allain S. 2021. Review of prey taken by anacondas (Squamata, Boidae: *Eunectes*). *Reptiles & Amphibians* 28:329–334. doi:[10.17161/randa.v28i2.15504](https://doi.org/10.17161/randa.v28i2.15504).

Thorbjarnarson J. 1995. Trailing the mythical anaconda. *Americas* 47:38–45.

Uetz P., Freed P., Aguilar R., Hosek J. 2022. The Reptile Database Accessible at <http://www.reptile-database.org>. Accessed on 28/10/2022.

Wetzel R.M. 1985. The identification and distribution of recent Xenarthra (= Edentata). Pp. 5–21, in Montgomery G.G. (Ed.). *The Evolution and Ecology of Armadillos, Sloths, and Vermilinguas*. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington.

Editor: Henrique C. Costa

Figure 1. Photographs of *Eunectes murinus* preying on *Bradypus variegatus* by constriction while hanging on tree branches in Caruari, Amazonas, Brazil.

Figure 2. Photographs of *Eunectes murinus* preying on an adult *Iguana iguana* by constriction while hanging on tree branches in Carreiro, Amazonas, Brazil.

